

ROLE OF SOCIETY IN CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

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ABSTRACT

Everyone has the right to live in this world and also every individual has responsibility to use natural resources judiciously. This will give equal opportunity to all to use the resources for the benefit of whole mankind. All living creatures belong to mother earth and they all have their shine of resources available. All these resources like land, energy, mineral, food, water, forest etc. have to be distributed in an equitable way for sustainable lifestyles of all creatures. Conservation of natural resources is now usually embraced in the broader conception of conserving the earth itself by protecting its capacity for self-renewal.

Finally, the aim of this paper is to highlight the importance of the role of society members in the conservation of our natural or environmental resources.

Keywords:

Natural resources, environmental resources, environment.

INTRODUCTION

The proper use of natural resources for long-lasting human welfare is known as conservation. The term natural resources includes all land, waters, vegetation, minerals and wildlife useful to the society in the maintenance of civilization. The wise and judicious use of natural resources without wasting them and the efforts of replacement like planting tree whenever possible are called conservation. The term conservation came into use in the late 19th century and referred to the management, mainly for economic reasons, of such valuable natural resources as fish, topsoil, pastureland and minerals and also to the preservation of forests, wilderness and watershed areas.

The important natural resources are as follows:

- Water is precious for life. It is stored for irrigation, domestic use, industrial use, mining and for other purposes. It is stored in porous soil, artesian wells and mountain streams. Lakes, oceans and rivers fulfill diverse human needs like food, recreation etc.
- Land is the basic resource. It serves as the storehouse of minerals, livestock, a home for wild animals, a producer of crops, a reservoir for water and a conserver of soil fertility.
- Minerals include useful components like gravel, coal, metals, oil, clay, sand, stone, phosphates, nitrates, etc.
- Top Soil is the fertile layer of soil. Productivity of agricultural crops, forest and fodder crops are dependent on this. The whole animal world is also dependent on it indirectly.

NEED FOR CONSERVATION

- Deforestation caused the loss of energy resources.

- Use of natural resources is increasing but the amount of these resources by decreasing.
- Relational and international capacities conserving the resources are not properly organized, must have some common conservation strategy.

OBJECTIVES OF CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

- To maintain the essential ecological processes i.e. food chain recycling of mineral resources etc.
- To ensure the availability and sustainability of resources which assumes the survival of all species is a healthy and easy manner.
- To preserve the diversity at the specific habitat levels.
- To maintain the essential life support system – soil, water, air, pond, plants and animals etc.

METHODS OF CONSERVATION OF RESOURCES

- Keeping the water taps closed, when not in use.
- Using less water-consuming toilets.
- Watering the plants to be done in the evening hours.
- Treating water to be provided for irrigation purpose.
- Avoiding wastage of energy.
- We should use the most efficient fuels available.
- Prevention of soil erosion by crop rotation, by growing erosion checking crops like grasses, ground nuts etc.

WAYS OF PROTECTING & PRESERVING OUR NATURAL RESOURCES

Natural resources are actually nature's gift to mankind to help us live a comfortable and peaceful life. But, at the same time, we as human beings have the responsibility of conserving natural resources by taking the right steps. This will help us maintain the environmental balance and satisfy our needs to the maximum. These days, the biggest concern before us is the fast reduction of natural resources such as water, natural gas, and forests. So, there are many important steps by which we can protect and preserve our natural resources on this earth-

- Plant vegetable on your own backyard. This will help you to prevent using cars to go to the market. This will also help in lessening air pollution.
- Don't throw trashes everywhere. This will help in lessening pollutions in air, water, and land.
- Turn off unused electric appliances. These will lessen the energy conserve and avoid global warming.
- Avoid using Liquefied Petroleum Gas. Instead use LPG has more chlorofluorocarbon than using charcoal. Charcoal is also much cheaper than LPG.
- Avoid throwing chemicals in different places. This can cause pollutions like air pollutions, water pollutions and land pollution.
- Recycle as many things as you can. Recycling things is the best way to lessen and avoid global warming and climate change.
- Try to educate local people for the protection and judicious use of natural resources.

CONCLUSION

Considering preservation and conservation of environment, the United States Environmental preservation is viewed or seen as the setting aside of earthly resources for preventing damage normally caused by contact with humans or by certain human activities, such as logging, mining, hunting, and fishing, only to replace them with new human activities such as tourism and recreation. Furthermore regulations and laws may be enacted for the preservation of natural resources. Being earth friendly is very essential as this will save our planet at the time making a better place to live in for us, for future generations.

The responsibility lies more on the human population because they have got the thinking power and the wisdom to judge good and had man should realize that he is not alone in this world. There are others to use the available resources. Hence responsibility should be for all human being for an equitable use of natural resources for sustainable use of natural resources for sustainable life styles of all in this mother earth.

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